

Accra's Air: What People Think and Want

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Executive Summary

Accra's Air: What People Think and Want

Air pollution in Accra is widely recognised as a serious environmental and health issue, yet little is known about how respondents prioritise the problem, where they place responsibility, and which types of policy responses they find acceptable. To address these questions, we conducted a city-wide survey in early 2025 with 1,750 respondents. The results offer new insights into public perceptions of air pollution, responsibility attribution, and support for a range of mitigation policies in Accra.

Air pollution is a top public concern: A large majority of Accra respondents are concerned about air pollution. About 72% of respondents said they were either “very” or “extremely” concerned about the issue. Concern was relatively consistent across gender and age groups, though respondents with higher education were more likely to say they were “extremely concerned.” However, when asked to rank the most important problems facing them, only 10% selected air pollution, placing it fifth behind economic condition, housing, road infrastructure, and corruption. This suggests that **while air quality is a widely acknowledged concern, it competes with other pressing personal daily challenges.**

Mitigation is a shared responsibility, with a strong role for local actors: When asked who should lead in addressing air pollution, 26% identified local government and 25% identified citizens. The national government (20%) and businesses (18%) were also seen as responsible, while international organisations and experts were rarely selected. Around 80% of respondents felt that **all three main domestic actors (local government, businesses, and citizens) are currently doing too little or not enough.** This suggests that respondents expect more involvement, especially at the local level.

Strong demand for most air pollution policies: Respondents expressed **strong support for a wide range of air pollution measures.** Fines for waste burning (87%) and increased information campaigns (84%), as well as stricter regulation of industries (81%) were particularly popular. Banning older vehicles (65%) received higher support than in many comparable cities. However, support was more mixed for infrastructure and cost-based measures such as expanding household electrification (56%) and public transport (48%). These differences suggest that **while the public is broadly supportive of regulatory and informational measures, support may be more conditional for policies that impose financial or behavioural costs.**

Key take-aways: Air pollution is a fairly serious concern among Accra respondents, even if it is not their top priority. People expect more action, particularly from local governments and citizens. There is strong public support for many air pollution policies, particularly those that target perceived sources of air pollution such as waste burning or polluting industries. However, cost-sensitive policies may face greater resistance unless designed in a way that addresses equity and accessibility concerns.

Based upon these findings, we identify several recommendations for policymakers and air pollution stakeholders in Accra:

1. Adopting policies with broad support, such as fines for waste burning, public information campaigns, and stricter regulation of industrial polluters.
2. Increasing support for less popular but impactful policies, such as household electrification and public transport expansion, by ensuring policies are perceived as fair, or as providing development co-benefits.
3. Building trust and shared ownership by clearly communicating the benefits of air pollution mitigation, and actively involving communities and local actors in policy design and implementation.

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Accra: City Overview

Between 2021 and 2023, average concentrations reached $33.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for on-the-ground PM_{10} and $25.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, respectively two times and five times higher than the WHO's annual limits. PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels decreased between 2021 and 2022, reaching their lowest point in July 2022. After that, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels plateaued, while PM_{10} began to increase, with levels still rising in 2023. Throughout this period, both pollutants consistently exceeded the World Health Organization's recommended safety guidelines.

Monthly PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ Levels, 2021-2023, Accra

Accra

\$5,150 GDP per Capita

12,197/km² Population Density

Ghana

0.57 Liberal Democracy V-Dem Index

0.44 Gini Coefficient

Accra is the largest city and the capital city of Ghana, which has relatively high levels of inequality globally (Gini: 0.44)².

Politically, Ghana is classified as an electoral democracy with a 0.57 score on the Liberal Democracy Index³. Accra has a population density⁴ of 12,197 people/km² and an estimated GDP per capita of \$5,150⁵.

In Ghana, Air Pollution Is Responsible for⁶:

About 22,000 Ghanaians are estimated to die prematurely due to air pollution every year⁷. Children are especially at risk, with about 38% of these deaths being under-five-year-olds in 2021⁸.

2025 Survey in Accra

We conducted surveys of residents in Accra between February and April 2025. Respondents were recruited through an online sample (n = 1,750) using the commercial panel provider Dynata. Quota-based sampling was applied to ensure the sample was representative of the city population with respect to age (18–59 years) and gender. To ensure data quality, the survey included two attention checks and enforced a minimum completion time based on the median from a soft launch.

Respondents who failed two or more quality checks were excluded from the final sample.

The sample consisted of 50% women and 50% men. The largest age group represented was 18–29 years, followed by the 30–39 and 40–49 groups. Due to the small number of respondents aged 50–59, this group was combined with the 40–49 group to create a 40–59 category. This age distribution reflects Ghana’s predominantly young population, where the median age is 21.

The most common education level among participants was a bachelor’s degree. Respondents were drawn from various areas across the city (see map above).

Education Level Distribution

Age Level Distribution

Salience of and Concern About Air Pollution

Salience of Air Pollution

For the first survey item, we presented respondents with a list of 10 problems that people in Accra could be facing. We then asked them to select 3 of the most important ones. Air pollution was the fifth most important problem in Accra, with 10% of respondents selecting it. Overall, the three most important problems were respondents' personal current economic condition, affordability of housing, and problems with road infrastructure.

Ranking of Most Important Problems in Accra:

1. Personal Economic Situation
2. Affordability of Housing
3. Problems With Road Infrastructure
4. Government Corruption
5. Air Pollution
6. Quality of Healthcare
7. Reliable and Affordable Access to Electricity
8. Public Safety
9. Access to Clean Water
10. Inequality and Discrimination

Concern About Air Pollution

Overall, a clear majority (82%) reported being either “very concerned” (57%) or “extremely concerned” (25%). An additional 16% were “somewhat concerned,” while fewer than 1% said they were “not at all concerned.”

The distribution of concern is broadly similar across gender and age groups, with only minor variations in the proportion of respondents expressing high concern.

However, differences by education level are more notable: respondents with higher education are more likely to say they are “extremely concerned” (28%), while those with lower education, who may be more directly exposed to air pollution, tend to report being “very concerned” (69%) rather than “extremely concerned” (14%).

Overall, the data indicate that concern about air pollution is widespread, with only modest socio-demographic variation in how intensely that concern is expressed.

Levels of Concern About Air Pollution by Socio-Demographics

Sources of Air Pollution

We presented respondents in Accra with a list of 8 potential sources of air pollution, and we asked them to select the three sources they think cause most pollution. Waste burning (1) and transportation (2) were perceived to contribute most to local air pollution. This is followed by industry (3), wildfire smoke, sand and dust (4), as well as construction (5).

*Other sources include sources such as shipping and solvents, and general other sources

In comparison to a scientific assessment of air pollution sources in Accra⁷, several sources identified by respondents show overlap, including wildfire smoke, sand and dust (1), waste burning (2), and transportation (5). However, other major contributors such as heating and cooking (3), as well as other sources (4), were less frequently mentioned by respondents.

These findings suggest a continuing mismatch between public perception and scientific assessments of air pollution sources. While respondents correctly identify key contributors such as waste burning and transportation, other significant sources - particularly household heating and cooking - remain largely unrecognised by the public. This disconnect underscores the need for targeted communication campaigns that clarify the true sources of air pollution. In Ghana, for example, biomass remains both the most affordable and culturally preferred cooking fuel⁹. Awareness efforts must therefore be paired with accessible alternatives, as understanding the risks alone is unlikely to drive change when “clean fuel” options are out of reach. Such campaigns are essential to support individual behaviour change and build wider public backing for government policies addressing air pollution.

Perceptions of Sources vs. Prioritisation of Action for Air Pollution

Building on the previous question about perceived sources of air pollution, this section explores whether these perceptions align with the actions people want their government to prioritise. The left side of the figure shows which sources respondents believe contribute most to air pollution, while the right side highlights which sources they think the government should focus on reducing.

Perceptions of Sources vs. Prioritisation of Action for Air Pollution

Overall, there is a broad alignment between perceived sources of air pollution and priorities for government action. For instance, many respondents identified construction as a source of pollution (9%) and a similar proportion (8%) wanted the government to prioritise it. However, several notable discrepancies also emerge.

In some cases, respondents were more likely to recognise a source but less likely to prioritise it for government action. For example, transportation - a major contributor to emissions in Accra's congested road network - was identified by 23% as a key source, yet only 21% listed it as a top government priority.

In other cases, the pattern is reversed: while just 19% viewed industry as a main source, 24% still wanted the government to focus on it, perhaps reflecting underlying concerns about emissions from factories or informal industrial activity.

These findings highlight both alignment and divergence between which sources respondents want the government to prioritise in mitigating pollution. They also point to a strong public mandate for action on key pollution sources in Accra, particularly waste burning, transportation, and industry, which are consistently seen as both major contributors to pollution and top priorities for government intervention.

Air Pollution Reduction Responsibilities

Who Is Responsible for Air Pollution Reduction?

Air Pollution Reduction

We asked respondents who they believed was most responsible for reducing air pollution, allowing them to select up to three institutional or societal actors.

Local government (26%) and citizens (25%) were most frequently named, suggesting that respondents see air pollution as a locally solvable issue, through both municipal policy and individual action. In Accra, where waste management, transport regulation, and urban planning depend on local implementation, this likely reflects the view that local engagement is essential to effective pollution reduction.

The national government (20%) and businesses (18%) were also frequently cited, indicating that broader leadership and private sector accountability are considered important. In contrast, experts (10%) and international organisations (2%) were mentioned far less often, suggesting a preference for local, visibly domestic solutions.

How Much Are Actors Doing to Reduce Air Pollution?

Action on Air Pollution Reduction

We also asked respondents how much local governments, businesses, and citizens are currently doing to reduce air pollution. Around 80% felt that all three groups are doing either “too little” or “not enough,” pointing to a broad sense that current efforts are insufficient.

A majority of respondents felt that more action is needed across all actors - 65% said businesses are not doing enough, followed by 64% for citizens and 61% for local governments.

These findings suggest that the public views air pollution reduction as a shared responsibility among government, businesses, and citizens. While local government is seen as the primary actor, businesses and citizens are also perceived as not doing enough. The public sees air pollution as a shared responsibility and supports more coordinated action, especially from local authorities, businesses, and individuals.

Public Demand for Air Pollution Policies

Public Demand for Air Pollution Policies

To better understand public preferences for government action on air pollution, we asked respondents to evaluate six distinct policy measures. These included stricter regulations, such as banning older vehicles or introducing fines for waste burning; low-cost interventions like providing information on health impacts; and moderately resource-intensive options, such as expanding public transport, promoting household electrification, and regulating polluting industries.

Overall, we find substantial support for many of these policies. Over 50% of respondents in Accra are either in favour or strongly in favour of policies to increase fines on waste burning (87%), provide more information (84%), further regulate polluting industries (81%), ban old vehicles (65%) and increase household electrification (56%). In particular, fines for waste burning and providing more information appear to have very broad support, with only 6% either being against or strongly against them.

This selection captures a range of approaches, from highly visible enforcement to informational and infrastructure-based strategies, and allows us to observe which types of measures are most publicly supported. For instance, the very high support for fines on waste burning (87%) suggests strong public backing for targeted enforcement. However, translating this support into action may still face challenges, such as limited enforcement capacity or unequal access to alternative waste management services.

Preferences towards expanding public transportation were more mixed. 48% of respondents in Accra were in favour of expanding public transportation, while 31% were against it. This suggests potential public pushback against policies that directly target individual behaviour, such as mobility.

Support for Regulating Industry by Socio-Demographics

Differences are more pronounced by education level: while 84% of highly educated respondents support this policy, support drops to 65% among those with lower education.

Despite this variation, support remains strong across all groups - suggesting that regulating industries is widely seen as a necessary step. One possible reason for this popularity is that the perceived benefits of action may outweigh the perceived costs, especially if respondents do not strongly associate regulation with higher prices or feel that industries can absorb the costs.

Electricity Access

Next, we explore how public support for the expansion of household electrification, even at the potential cost of higher electricity prices, varies across socio-demographic groups. Overall, the policy is supported by a majority (56%), as indicated by the dashed line in the figure. Support is slightly higher among men (61%) than women (52%), and somewhat lower among respondents aged 18–29 (54%).

Support varies modestly by education level, with respondents with lower education somewhat more supportive (62%) than those with higher education (56%).

This may reflect different lived experiences: those with higher education are more likely to already have reliable electricity access, while those with lower education may view household electrification as a more immediate and personally relevant benefit.

While the policy is backed by majorities across all groups, lower support among women and those with higher education suggests more ambivalence. This may reflect differing perceptions of the policy's costs and benefits across groups.

Regulations on Industry

How do individual policy preferences vary by socio-demographic characteristics? The dashed line in the figure represents the overall support for regulating industries, a high 81%, even when framed as potentially leading to higher consumer prices.

Support levels are broadly consistent across gender: 80% of women and 82% of men are in favour. Looking at age, support peaks among 30–39 year-olds (86%) and is slightly lower among 18–29 year-olds (78%).

Support for Expanding Electricity Access by Socio-Demographics

Public Transportation

We examined public support for expanding public transportation funded through higher ticket prices. This measure had the lowest support of all policies tested, with only 48% of respondents in favour (see dashed line). While support was fairly consistent across groups, some patterns stand out.

Men (54%) were more supportive than women (42%), suggesting gendered differences in perceived safety or cost sensitivity. Support peaked among 40–59 year-olds (57%) and was lowest among 18–29 year-olds (43%), possibly reflecting dissatisfaction with services or skepticism about fare increases leading to improvements.

Educational differences were modest but notable: support was highest among highly educated respondents (51%) and lowest among those with medium education (44-45%), perhaps reflecting different levels of trust in government capacity.

Overall, moderate support may stem from affordability concerns or doubts about service quality. In Accra, where congestion is severe, improved public transport could reduce pollution, but resistance may persist among younger residents who rely on affordable fares and among those for whom car ownership signals status and independence.

Support for Expanding Public Transportation by Socio-Demographics

Ban on Old Vehicles

By contrast, banning older, more polluting vehicles enjoys strong public support, with 65% of respondents in favour, among the highest for all policies tested. Support is especially high among women (68%) and young adults (65–67%), groups often most affected by poor air quality and mobility constraints.

Compared to cost-based measures like fare hikes, this preference suggests support for clear, enforceable actions that directly target visible pollution sources such as aging cars and minibuses.

Support is strongest among those with medium (63%) and high (67%) education but drops to 50% among respondents with lower education, possibly reflecting greater reliance on older vehicles or less access to environmental information.

Overall, the policy likely resonates due to widespread awareness of aging vehicles' role in Accra's congestion and pollution. In a city where smoky, unreliable vehicles are common, such a ban is seen as a practical step toward cleaner transport.

Support for Banning Old Vehicles by Socio-Demographics

Air Pollution Policy Support Across Middle-Income Cities

We also compare support levels for air pollution policies in Accra to those in three major middle-income cities: Johannesburg (South Africa), Jakarta (Indonesia), and Delhi (India).

Comparison of Air Pollution Policy Support in Middle-Income Cities

In Accra, attitudes toward air pollution policies are generally positive, though support varies depending on the type of measure. Notably, respondents expressed the strongest support for fines on waste burning (87%), a level comparable to Delhi (87%) and Jakarta (89%), and slightly higher than in Johannesburg (82%). Support for providing more information was also high in Accra and broadly in line with levels observed across the other three cities.

Interestingly, support for banning older vehicles in Accra (65%) is notably higher than in Johannesburg (37%), but lower than in Jakarta (67%) and Delhi (82%). This suggests that Accra's public is relatively open to regulatory approaches, even if support does not reach the levels seen in some other cities.

In Accra, 56% of respondents support expanding electricity access, a level identical to Johannesburg (56%) and similar to Jakarta (54%), but noticeably lower than in Delhi (75%). Support for investment in public transport is more limited, with 48% in favour, below Jakarta (61%) and Delhi (68%), but slightly higher than Johannesburg (45%). These patterns suggest that while there is a foundation of public support in Accra for infrastructure-focused policies, overall backing remains moderate. This could pose challenges for advancing more ambitious initiatives without further public engagement or careful policy design that responds to local priorities and constraints.

Respondents in Accra, Johannesburg, Jakarta and Delhi have different perceptions and policy preferences regarding air pollution, showing the importance of tailoring interventions to local priorities, economic realities, and perceived effectiveness. Public support for air pollution policies in Accra is strong.

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